

REACTION OF GLYCEROPHOSPHORIC ACID AND ORTHOPHOSPHORIC ACID WITH ISOELECTRIC GELATIN STUDIED BY PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS

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The amount of either glycerophosphoric acid or orthophosphoric acid, bound with 1 g. of isoelectric gelatin at 37°, is found to be 80.40×10^{-4} g. mol., as determined from the minima of the plateau of the graphs obtained by plotting bound H^+ ions against the equilibrium p_{H} value of the mixture of gelatin sol and the solutions of the respective acids of concentrations, 0.002-0.016 M; this combination corresponds to 0.01M initial concentration of either acid, at which both are found to be ionised as monobasic acids. The conductometric titration and viscosity curves also show inflections at points corresponding to 0.01M initial concentration. In addition to chemical combination of both the acids with gelatin, there is also adsorption of the acid molecules, side by side, at p_{H} value below 2.73 in the case of glycerophosphoric acid and below 2.8 in the case of orthophosphoric acid

In the formation of protein salts with strong acids, the anion of the acid may be co-ordinately bound at the NH_2 groups, forming NH_2X , in which one H has a four-electron shell as in HFP_2 , according to Phillips (*J. Int. Soc. Leather Trades Chem.*, 1933, 17, 15, 69). Schellaman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 67, 472) attributes the binding of anions to proteins to the low dielectric constant of protein film sheathing by Coulomb's force. Pauli and Modern (*Biochem. Z.*, 1925, 166, 482) observed that only acids with ionisation constants greater than that of the carboxyl groups of the proteins (*i.e.* with a value for $pK=4$) would be able to form salts with the proteins. In the case of orthophosphoric acid, which ionised in three stages [(1) $K^1=0.8 \times 10^{-2}$; (2) $K^2 = 2.0 \times 10^{-7}$; (3) $K''' = 3.6 \times 10^{-12}$] it was anticipated by Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1918-19, 1, 39, 327, 559) and Hitchcock (*ibid.*, 1922, 4, 733), but not verified, that like HCl and $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, it would react with proteins as a monobasic acid. The object of the present work is to verify experimentally the above mentioned statement by studying potentiometric and conductometric titrations and viscosity changes of 1% aqueous solutions of isoelectric gelatin in presence of 0.2-1.6 m. mol./100 c.c. (corresponding to 0.002-0.016 M solutions) of orthophosphoric acid and glycerophosphoric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of Merck's chemically pure quality. Isoelectric gelatin supplied by M/s. Kodak Ltd., London, having an ash value of 0.025% and giving an aqueous solution of p_{H} 4.66 at 37°, was used; CO_2 -free distilled water (p_{H} 6.8) was used for preparing the solutions of the gelatin and the acids.

All measurements of physical properties were carried out in a thermostat with a toluene-mercury thermoregulator at $37^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Ostwald's viscometer was used for viscosity measurements; Kohlrausch's bridge, for measuring electrical conductivity; Hydrogen electrode (Bunker's type), to measure the p_{H} value of the solutions; and a potentiometer, reading to 0.2 millivolts, was used for measuring the E.M.F.

By studying the influence of dilution on the p_H value of the aqueous solutions of glycerophosphoric and orthophosphoric acids, it was found that the former ionised as monobasic up to 0.01 M and dibasic up to 0.002 M , while the latter as monobasic up to 0.008 M and dibasic up to 0.002 M .

The results of potentiometric titrations of 1% isoelectric gelatin solution against glycerophosphoric and orthophosphoric acids respectively are shown in Table I; 50 c.c. of glycerophosphoric acid or orthophosphoric acid of various molarities (0.004 to 0.032) were diluted to 100 c.c. with (1) CO_2 -free distilled water and (2) 2% isoelectric gelatin solution; the p_H values in the two cases were determined and the difference in H^+ ion concentration in 100 c.c. represented the amount of H^+ ions bound to 1 g. of gelatin.

$$\text{No. of g. equiv. of the acid bound} = \frac{\text{amt. of } H^+ \text{ ions bound}}{\text{degree of ionisation}};$$

$$\text{No. of g. mol. of the bound acid} = \frac{\text{No. of g. equiv. bound}}{\text{basicity of the acid}}$$

The plots of H^+ ions bound with 1 g. of gelatin against the p_H values of the mixture of 1% gelatin solution and various amounts of the acids are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

The conductometric titration curves for the two acids and the viscosity changes, represented by $\rho \times t$, where ρ = sp. gr. and t = time of flow, on addition of various amounts of the acid to 1 g. of gelatin are shown in Fig. 2.

TABLE I

Potentiometric titration of 100 c.c. of 1% gelatin soln. against glycerophosphoric acid and orthophosphoric acid at 37°

Acid (m mol./100 c.c. aq. soln.)	Degree of ionisation of the acid.	p_H of the aq. soln. of the acid.	$[H] \times 10^3$ of the aq. soln.	p_H of the mixture of the acid & gela- tin soln.	$[H] \times 10^3$ of the mixture.	Amt. of H ions bound $\times 10^3$.	G. mol. of the bound acid $\times 10^3$.
(1) Glycerophosphoric acid.							
Dibasic.							
0.2	1.00	2.33	450	4.15	7.08	45.29	22.64
0.4	0.86	2.16	690	3.61	24.55	66.54	38.68
0.6	0.71	2.07	850	3.30	50.12	79.98	56.32
0.8	0.56	2.05	890	2.93	117.50	77.20	68.92
Monobasic.							
1.0	0.95	2.02	950	2.73	185.20	76.38	80.40
1.2	0.92	1.95	1170	2.56	275.48	84.45	88.53
1.6	0.84	1.87	1350	2.33	467.70	87.23	103.84
Dibasic. (2) Orthophosphoric acid.							
Dibasic.							
0.2	1.00	2.33	450	4.15	7.08	45.29	22.64
0.4	0.83	2.19	650	3.75	17.78	53.22	30.85
0.6	0.62	2.14	750	3.40	39.81	68.02	58.85
Monobasic.							
0.8	0.95	2.12	760	3.06	87.10	67.29	70.83
1.0	0.81	2.09	810	2.80	158.50	65.15	80.43
1.2	0.76	2.05	890	2.67	213.81	67.62	88.97
1.6	0.69	1.96	1100	2.39	407.40	69.26	101.82

DISCUSSION

On plotting combined H^+ ions against the equilibrium p_H values of the mixtures of glycerophosphoric acid and gelatin, the curve shown in Fig. 1 has a minimum in the plateau at p_H 2.73, corresponding to 76.38×10^{-3} g. equiv. of H^+ ions bound to 1 g. of gelatin. In case of orthophosphoric acid, the curve obtained is similar and has a minimum in the plateau at p_H 2.8, corresponding to 65.15×10^{-3} g. equiv. of H^+ ions bound to 1 g. of gelatin. Both these p_H values correspond to the same initial concentration of the two acids, 0.01 M. Again, the amount of the g. mois. of the acid bound to 1 g. of gelatin in the case of either acid is exactly the same, 80.4×10^{-3} . The g. eq. weight of gelatin, calculated from this value on the basis of the combination of the acids as monobasic, is 1243.6. The amount of H^+ ions bound being different while that of the acid bound being the same, it may be concluded that there is molecular rather than ionic combination between gelatin and the acids. In case of gelatin and hydrochloric acid a similar combination curve was obtained by Atkin and Douglas (*J. Int. Soc. Leather Trades Chem.*, 1924, 8, 359). This shows that the phosphoric acids behave like strong acids at high dilution.

After the complete combination, the continuous increase in the amount of combined acid with increase in initial concentration of the acid may be attributed to adsorption of molecules of the acid to form adsorption complexes as concluded by Sinclair and Gortner (*Cereal Chem.*, 1933, 10, 171) in case of gliadin and acetic acid.

Fig. 2 shows that in presence of 1% gelatin solution, the specific conductivity increases gradually with increase in concentration of glycerophosphoric acid up to 0.008 M and of orthophosphoric acid up to 0.01 M, after which there is a sudden increase and inflection in the curve; this means that the combination is complete at these concentrations which are the same as in the case of the potentiometric titration.

The plots of $p \times t$ against concentration of the acids added to 1% gelatin solution show that viscosity goes on increasing rapidly with concentration of the acid added up to 0.01M and then decreases gradually. The increase in viscosity can be attributed to the increase in the production of positively charged gelatin ions on combination with the acid. In addition to electro-viscous effect, according to Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 721) the ions are hydrated and consequent increase in diameters retards their flow. On comparing Figs. 1 and 2 and referring to Table I, it is observed that the p_n corresponding to maxima of viscosity curve coincides nearly with that of the minima of plateau of the combination curve.

On comparing the plots of viscosity and electrical conductivity (Fig. 2) it is observed that there is a reversal behaviour of specific conductance with respect to viscosity in case of the two acids; this is in accordance with the equation derived by Krasny-Ergen (*Kolloid Z.*, 1936, **74**, 172) in which the specific viscosity of the solution varies *inversely* as its specific conductance. It has been verified experimentally that the ionic conductivity of glycerophosphoric anion is greater than that of the orthophosphoric anion.

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